

Alkali-Metal Complexes : Adducts of Alkali-Metal Salts of O-Nitro-phenol and 8-Hydroxyquinoline with α -Benzoin-monoxime

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Cupron or α -benzoinmonoxime form coloured complexes with many transition metals. The green compound formed with copper has been used as a specific test for copper and widely applied in analytical chemistry.

EXTENDING the work on alkali metal complexes we now present the synthesis of the adducts of alkali metal salts of *o*-nitrophenol (ONP) and 8-hydroxyquinoline (8HQ) with α -benzoinmonoxime (BzmX). We have chosen the ligand cupron with the view that since it has both the donor groups -OH and -NOH, there could be the possibility of double hydrogen bonding.

Experimental

Adducts of alkali metal salts of 8HQ and ONP with α -Benzoinmonoxime: α -Benzoinmonoxime was added to a abs. ethanol solution of alkali metal salts of 8-hydroxyquinoline/*o*-nitrophenol. The solution was warmed for 5 minutes on a steam bath and allowed to cool. After several minutes the yellow compounds (of Li, Na, K, Rb and Cs) which formed were filtered off, with absolute ethanol and dried in an oven at 80°.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes are stable only when stored under dry condition. On exposure to moisture, hydrolysis of the complex to the free ligand and metal salt appeared to take place. This was confirmed by chemical analysis and infrared spectra.

The colour, decomposition temperatures and analytical results of the complexes are given in Table 1. On the basis of the evidence given below, we conclude that the solid adducts are definite compounds and not mixtures^{1,2}. The decomposition temperature of the complexes were higher than melting point of second ligand (α -benzoinmonoxime) as is apparent from Table 1. Physical mixtures of the salts of 8HQ and α -benzoinmonoxime, (mole ratio, 1:1) have melting points at 145°, 143°, 142°, 145°, and 141° for metals Li, Na, K, Rb and Cs respectively (cf. m.p. for BzmX = 151°).

Infrared measurements were made in Nujol mulls for the ligand and complexes between 4000-650 cm⁻¹. Selected absorption bands in different regions are given in Table 2.

It is reported³ that the group >C=NOH has an absorption band at 1660 in α -benzoinmonoxime and its copper(II) salt exhibits one >C=N at 1545 cm⁻¹ whereas copper(II) and nickel(II) complexes of α -benzoinmonoxime have two C=N- bands at 1650 and 1550 cm⁻¹. This indicates that they are not equivalent. Their salts do not show any OH bands. In 1952, Rundle and Parsol⁴ noted that the OH stretching band of dimethylglyoxime (DMG-H) near 3100 cm⁻¹ is shifted to 1775 cm⁻¹ in Ni(DMG)₂. This extra ordinarily low OH stretching frequency was attributed to strong hydrogen bonding, since they observed that, as the OH...O distance decreases, the OH stretching frequency becomes lower in a series of compounds in which the OH...O distance varies progressively. Later, Nakamoto *et al.*⁵ extended similar "frequency distance relationships" to other hydrogen bond system such as NH...O and OH...N.

The spectra of the α -benzoinmonoxime complexes with alkali metal salts of organic acids also show number of unexpected features. (a) One of the O-H stretching frequency of the second ligand is missing, and the other O-H stretching frequency is shifted down by about 150 cm⁻¹. (b) A new broad band of medium intensity with submaxima at 2700 cm⁻¹ in all the complexes and another at 2600 cm⁻¹ are seen in most of the complexes, which are the two ingradients. The peaks between 2600-2700 cm⁻¹ have been assigned to N...H...O bonding in 8HQ complexes^{6,7}. (c) Another new strong band around 1850 cm⁻¹ is seen in the ONP complexes, which is assigned to strong hydrogen bonding⁸.

The other spectral data indicate that the absorption frequencies are perturbed on complex formation. A weak maxima at 1660 cm⁻¹, assigned to

TABLE-1 SOME PROPERTIES AND ANALYTICAL DATA.

Compound	Colour	Decomposition temperature (°C)	Found				Calculated			
			C	H	N	M	C	H	N	M
Li8HQ.BzmX	Pale yellow	168	72.9	5.2	7.5		73.0	5.1	7.4	
Na8HQ.BzmX	Yellow	167	70.4	4.6	7.0	5.97	0.0	4.8	7.1	5.8
K8HQ.BzmX	Yellow	164	68.1	4.4	6.9	9.5	67.3	4.6	6.8	9.5
Rb8HQ.BzmX	Yellow	160	60.1	4.4	6.0	18.8	60.4	4.2	6.1	18.7
Cs8HQ.BzmX	Yellow	155	53.9	4.3	5.4	26.7	54.8	3.8	5.5	26.3
NaONP.BzmX	Orange	185	61.4	4.6	7.1	5.7	61.8	4.4	7.2	5.9
KONP.BzmX	Yellow	181	59.0	4.4	6.8	10.1	59.4	4.2	6.9	9.6
RbONP.BzmX	Pale yellow	172	52.9	3.8	6.3	18.8	53.2	3.8	6.2	18.9
CsONP.BzmX	Yellow	160	48.3	3.3	5.5	26.4	48.2	3.4	5.6	26.7

TABLE-2 SELECTED IR ABSORPTION BANDS (IN CM⁻¹)

Compound	Above 3000 (O-H)	3000	2700-2500 (N.....H.....O/O.....H.....O)	1900-1800 (O.....H.....O)	1700-1600 (C=N)	(N-O)
BzmX=L	3300sh	3230			1660w	985
Li8HQ.L		3100	2720	2610	1650w	975
Na8HQ.L		3150	2700	2620	1645w	1600
K 8HQ.L		3150		2650	1655w	1600
Rb8HQ.L			2720	2600	1650w	1605
Cs8HQ.L			2710	2620	1655w	1600
NaONP.L	3320			2650	1640w	1600
K ONP.L		3150	2700		1640w	1600
RbONP.L		3180	2700		1650w	1605
CsONP.L		3150		2660	1655w	1605

C=N grouping, is shifted by 10-15 cm⁻¹ in the complexes and its intensity is also reduced. The medium peaks at 985 cm⁻¹ in the ligand assigned to N-O stretching vibrations, shift between 985-970 cm⁻¹ in the complexes. These changes in the absorption frequencies for C=N grouping and N-O stretching vibrations confirm the donation of a lone pair from the nitrogen atom to the metal to form chelate.

From a comparative study of infrared spectra of these compounds, we observed, that the hydrogen bonding is an essential feature for forming these solid adducts. None of these mixed ligand complexes show anomalous broad absorption band between 1100-700 cm⁻¹, as such the acid salt structure⁸ with very short O...H...O (ca., 2.4 Å) is most improbable. The observed change in the frequency of the

ligating groups of different second ligand molecules with decrease bond order, points the coordination sites through O- and N- atom to the metal to form chelates.

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